

Original Article

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (Kap) Study Towards Family Planning among Women in Rural Areas of Multan

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Abstract

This study examines the family planning knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of women in rural Multan, Pakistan. 200 women aged 18 to 45 participated in the survey, providing significant insights on their knowledge, attitudes, and utilization of family planning methods. Structured interviews employed a pre-tested questionnaire to find out how participants felt about using birth control, how much they knew about different methods, and what they really did to plan their families in their daily lives. The results indicate that while most women were familiar with family planning methods, there was a notable deficiency in their comprehensive awareness of the many types of contraception and their respective benefits and drawbacks. There were good feelings about family planning, and many women said that contraception is important for improving health, family well-being, and economic stability. Despite these favorable feelings, the main reasons for the low use of family planning methods were sociocultural barriers, limited access to healthcare facilities, and a lack of support from family or partners. The research stresses the need for enhanced health education programs for women in rural areas, with an emphasis on dispelling myths and giving them all the information they need about family planning methods. To make contraception more accepted and used in rural regions, it is important to promote family planning activities in the community and improve healthcare infrastructure.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Family Planning, Rural Women, Multan, Contraception, Reproductive Health

Introduction

Family planning allows a couple to freely and responsibly choose how many children to have and how far apart to have them, and it has been shown to be an effective method of improving both mother and child health. Family planning has also important implications in population dynamics. World population is anticipated to increase 9.1 billion by the year 2025. According to the Pakistan fertility and family planning survey 1997, the contraceptive rate in the country is only 24 even though 94% of people are aware of at least one family planning strategy. Pakistan, which has a population of 130.6 million as of 1998, is the sixth most populous country in the world and is growing by 2.4% a year. Currently, Pakistan is experiencing high rates of maternal and infant mortality.

Family planning empowers individuals and couples to decide if and when they want to have children, using the knowledge, tools, and support they need. It includes a wide range of contraceptive methods like pills, implants, IUDs, surgical procedures, and barrier methods such as condoms. There are also non-invasive

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approaches like abstinence and tracking fertility through the calendar method. Family planning isn't just about preventing pregnancy, it also helps people who want to conceive by providing guidance and support, including access to infertility treatments. Organizations like UNFPA play a key role in this effort by supporting voluntary access to contraception, training healthcare providers to offer counseling, and promoting age-appropriate, comprehensive sexuality education in schools (Ejembi, 2015).

According to Women's Health Care, family planning is about couples making informed decisions on when to have children, how many to have, and how to space their pregnancies—often with the help of contraceptive methods. Yet, despite the availability of these methods, over 200 million women in developing countries want to avoid pregnancy but are not using effective contraception.

This gap exists even though many contraceptives, like condoms, not only prevent pregnancy but also reduce the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and help avoid the pain, risks, and costs associated with unsafe abortions. Tragically, unsafe abortions in these regions still account for a significant number of pregnancy-related deaths among both mothers and infants. Despite the clear benefits of family planning, its use remains limited in many developing countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) highlights several barriers: limited access to contraceptive options, fear of side effects, cultural and religious opposition, and a lack of proper education and support. Bias and incorrect information from healthcare practitioners often make people less likely to get family planning services (Lincoln, 2018).

Planning for families is an important part of public health. It includes ways and plans that help people or couples figure out how many kids they want and when they want them. It helps people attain their reproductive goals by making sure that pregnancies are planned and occurring at the right times. There are both short-term and long-term family planning options. Short-term methods include condoms, birth control pills, and intrauterine devices (IUDs). Long-term approaches include sterilization. These methods are meant to meet the requirements and wants of different people, so that individuals and couples can make informed choices that fit their situations and life goals. Moreover, family planning is closely linked to a number of broader social and economic benefits. It can help fight poverty and protect the environment by controlling population growth (Pierre, 2010). This is because it gives women the power to look for jobs and education.

According to the Punjab Welfare Department, family planning includes a range of practices that help couples avoid unintended pregnancies, plan for children when they are ready, space births appropriately, and decide how many children they want to have taking into account their health, age, and life circumstances. The World Health Organization (WHO) further defines family planning as a way for individuals and couples to achieve their goals regarding the number, timing, and spacing of their children. This is made possible through the use of contraceptives and support for those facing infertility. Over the past two decades, increased access to family planning and contraceptive methods has helped reduce maternal deaths in developing countries by 40%. Experts estimate that by meeting the unmet need for family planning, especially by preventing unplanned pregnancies, another 30% of maternal deaths could be prevented. In short, family planning is not just about controlling births, it's about giving people the knowledge and tools to make informed, healthy choices for themselves and their families (Ali, 2019).

Currently, family planning services in the country are offered through both public and private sectors, with public facilities providing contraceptives free of charge. However, despite ongoing investments in family planning programs, contraceptive use remains low.

According to the National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), awareness about contraceptive methods is generally high, but actual usage is limited. Only 15% of married women of reproductive age use any form of contraception, and just 10% use modern methods. Meanwhile, the unmet need for contraception stands at 16%. Promoting family planning in countries with high birth rates can have a powerful impact. In addition to preventing 32% of all maternal fatalities and over 10% of child deaths, it can aid in the reduction of poverty and famine. There are several advantages to family planning services for society at large as well as for individual women. These services contribute significantly to the protection of mothers' and children's health by reducing unsafe abortions and preventing unwanted pregnancies. In the end, particularly in poorer

nations, successful family planning initiatives can drop fertility rates and help to lower maternal mortality (Ejembe, 2015).

One important public health concern that has a big influence on women's health, socioeconomic standing, and general well-being is family planning. Developing successful solutions to support reproductive health and guarantee that women have control over their reproductive choices requires an understanding of women's family planning knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP).

OBJECTIVES:

- To analyze the Level/proportion of women's knowledge about family planning in Multan city.
- To determine the impact of women's attitude towards family planning.
- To determine the Level/ratio of women practices about the use of family planning methods.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

SOCIAL COGNITIVE THEORY

The Family Planning Feedback Concept, put forth by Davis and Blake in 1956, serves as the theoretical cornerstone of this investigation. This concept states that knowledge, motivation, and appraisal are the three main factors that go into decisions about fertility regulation. Understanding the alternatives available for regulating reproductive behavior is the first step. Although information is crucial, it is insufficient on its own to affect the use of contraceptives; perceptions of the availability and accessibility of contraceptive techniques must also be present. Women must think that contraceptive techniques are not only practical but also affordable for them to use on a daily basis if they are to take the practice seriously.

Motivation, or the desire or readiness to regulate fertility, is the second element. Numerous elements, such as family life cycle stages, cultural beliefs, and socioeconomic situation, influence motivation. According to economic theories of fertility, motivation is the equilibrium between the supply and demand for children, which is impacted by social and personal factors. Assessment is the last phase, during which people consider the advantages and disadvantages of utilizing contraception. Before choosing a choice, this stage entails giving considerable thought to social, personal, and health-related aspects. In conclusion, the Davis and Blake model highlights that information, motivation, and critical evaluation are all essential components that influence reproductive behavior and are necessary for making successful family planning decisions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to a study by Singh (2016) family planning initiatives have been crucial in lowering fertility rates and are anticipated to contribute to the stabilization of population growth soon. These campaigns have been successful in raising public awareness of family planning techniques, even though they may not have fully accomplished their objectives. Media exposure was one of the major factors influencing women's decisions to use family planning because it shaped attitudes and closed the knowledge, attitude, and practice gap (also known as the KAP gap). In addition, women's decision to use family planning techniques was significantly influenced by their health.

According to a study by Gage (2022) the socio-economic and cultural factors play a significant role in contraceptive use, especially in African contexts. Her research also examined how education and gender norms affect the adoption of family planning methods. Patriarchal gender norms shape many aspects of family planning, including fertility rates, the timing of marriage and childbirth, desired family size, preferences for the sex and order of children, medical restrictions related to family planning (such as access to safe abortion), and the age at which girls marry including the issue of child marriage.

According to a study by Johnson (2016) women's awareness of family planning was high, but their actual usage of contraceptives was still low. Fear of side effects was the most often stated excuse for not utilizing family planning techniques, especially among people who had unfavorable opinions about contraception. Conflicts with religious beliefs and a lack of consideration were two additional major reasons

why people didn't utilize it. More than half of the people who answered the survey had finished at least high school, which may have helped them understand and regulate how to use oral contraceptives better.

Jain (2021) examined the influence of various factors on fertility and family planning behaviors. He discovered that psychological characteristics included contentment with fundamental needs, robust ideals pertaining to personal growth, and the preservation of an open-minded disposition. Ramesh discovered that a person's domicile, income, education, and overall socioeconomic status significantly affect their fertility and family planning decisions. These factors, on the other hand, do not have a direct effect on fertility and family planning. Instead, they use the psychological traits that were mentioned before to change these habits. For example, people who are happy with their basic needs or who have a positive attitude about personal growth may be more inclined to make different decisions about family planning than others who don't have these attributes.

Warwick (2023) reported that Indonesia's family planning program has been successful by engaging communities, persuading clients, providing medical support, and maintaining strong pressure for results. Data from 48 villages show that these strategies effectively encourage and sustain the use of contraceptives. However, the program faces challenges, including measuring success, balancing external influence with client autonomy, managing pressure on government agencies, and keeping local commitment. The future of the program will depend on whether Indonesia continues to support it as strongly as it has since 1970.

Mushy (2020) studied that why young women in Tanzania still face problems with unwanted pregnancies, even though modern family planning methods are available. Although all 15 participants knew about different contraceptives, many didn't use them. They were worried about side effects like cancer, infertility, and weight gain. He found several reasons why they didn't use family planning, such as myths and misconceptions, a shortage of healthcare providers, and the unavailability of their preferred methods. Also, their close friends and partners had a huge impact on their choice not to use birth control.

According to Bekele and Surur (2020), women's opinions and knowledge had a substantial impact on how many women of reproductive age used family planning. Women with greater knowledge were more inclined to utilize family planning methods compared to those with lesser information. People who thought family planning was a good thing were more likely to utilize it than people who thought it was a bad thing. This means that having the right attitudes and information is very important for starting and keeping up with family planning activities. Furthermore, among women of reproductive age, the use of family planning was linked to factors like where they lived, whether they were married or single, their job, their level of education, their age, the size of their family, and their average monthly income.

Sultan (2018) discovered that the perceptions and behaviors regarding the utilization of family planning methods significantly influence their effectiveness. He says that changing these attitudes and habits at their foundation is very vital if family planning is going to work even better. The research indicates that a significant issue is the persistent stigma associated with the negative effects of birth control. This stigma may make it tougher for people to employ these methods on a regular basis, which could be bad for both individual and public health. He emphasized that good communication is always important for changing how both men and women think about family planning methods. He thinks that some styles of communication can make birth control far more acceptable and useful.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN

The study utilized a cross-sectional descriptive research approach, suitable for evaluating the existing knowledge, attitudes, and practices of women in rural Multan. A cross-sectional approach provided a temporal snapshot of the population, facilitating the identification of associations and the comprehension of the distribution of numerous characteristics pertaining to family planning.

STUDY AREA

This study was carried out in the rural regions of Multan District, concentrating on Suraj Miani, Sikandri Nala, and the vicinity of Head Muhammad Wala Bridge.

STUDY POPULATION

The study population consisted of 310 married women aged 18 to 49 residing in the rural regions of Multan. The reason this group was chosen is that married women in this age range are the ones who make the most decisions about family planning. Women of reproductive age were the target population since they were most likely to be involved in family planning activities, like using birth control or making plans for future children.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Married women between the ages of 18 and 49.
- Women who resided in rural areas of Multan district.
- Women who were willing to participate in the study and provide informed consent.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Women who were unable to comprehend the survey questions or communicate well;
- Women who were pregnant or nursing, as their requirements about family planning may differ.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The study utilized a multistage random sampling technique to ensure a representative sample from the rural parts of Multan, necessitating several phases.

- **Stage 1 (Selection of Villages):** The initial stage was to choose rural areas (towns or villages) in Multan at random. A random sampling method, such as a random number generator, was used to pick a specified number of rural areas from a list of all the places based on the desired sample size.
- **Stage 2 (Selection of homes):** After choosing the villages, the next step was to choose the homes. A list of the homes in the chosen villages was made, and a simple random selection method was used to choose some of them to take part in the study.
- **Stage 3 (Selection of Participants):** A woman of reproductive age was selected from each chosen household to participate in the study. If there were more than one lady in a home who could be picked, one was chosen at random.

Statistical power calculations were used to figure out the sample size such that the results would be meaningful. This computation used a 5% margin of error, a 95% confidence level, and a 50% prevalence for the worst-case scenario to figure out the expected prevalence of knowledge, attitude, and practice.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL

The data collection instrument was a structured, pre-tested questionnaire specifically designed to obtain information about women's knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to family planning.

DATA ANALYSIS

After collecting the data, the answers were coded and put into statistical software like SPSS or STATA so that they could be analyzed.

- **DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS:** Frequencies and percentages were calculated to summarize the women's knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding family planning.
- **CHI-SQUARE TESTS:** To determine associations between socio-demographic factors (e.g., age, education level, socioeconomic status) and family planning knowledge, attitude, and practice.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of participants' rights:

- **INFORMED CONSENT:** Written or verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants.
- **CONFIDENTIALITY:** All personal information collected during the study remained confidential. Participant identities were not disclosed in any reports or publications.

RESULTS

TABLE 1: ACCESS TO FAMILY PLANNING COUNSELING OR INFORMATION IN YOUR AREA

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE%
Strongly agree	56	18.0%
Agree	115	38.0%
Disagree	93	30.0%
Strongly disagree	47	14.0%

CHI-SQUARE VALUE: $\chi^2 = 39.0$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$

INTERPRETATION: 51.2% report having access to counseling or information, but a substantial 49.8% do not. This indicates gaps in information services that need to be addressed.

TABLE 2: EVER CONSULTED A HEALTHCARE PROVIDER ABOUT FAMILY PLANNING METHODS

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE%
Strongly agree	78	25.0%
Agree	140	45.0%
Disagree	62	20.0%
Strongly disagree	30	9.6%

CHI-SQUARE VALUE: $\chi^2 = 87.4$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$

INTERPRETATION: 70.4% have consulted healthcare providers about family planning, which is relatively high. This suggests that when services are available, women do seek professional advice.

TABLE 3: DOES UNPLANNED PREGNANCY AFFECT YOUR LIFE?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE%
Strongly agree	78	25.0%
Agree	139	44.0%
Disagree	62	20.0%
Strongly disagree	31	10.0%

CHI-SQUARE VALUE: $\chi^2 = 79.3$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$

INTERPRETATION: This indicates a statistically significant difference between the observed and expected frequencies. The majority of women (70%) agree or strongly agree that an unplanned pregnancy affects their life, highlighting the profound impact such pregnancies can have.

TABLE 4: ARE YOU AWARE THAT FAMILY PLANNING METHODS CAN PREVENT UNINTENDED PREGNANCIES

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE%
Strongly agree	70	25.0%
Agree	147	44.0%
Disagree	62	20.0%
Strongly disagree	31	10.0%

CHI-SQUARE VALUE: $\chi^2 = 94.0$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$

INTERPRETATION: The majority of women (70%) agree or strongly agree that an unplanned pregnancy affects their life, highlighting the profound impact such pregnancies can have.

CONCLUSION

This study on family planning among rural women in Multan reveals that while awareness of contraceptive methods is relatively high, significant knowledge gaps and social barriers—such as religious concerns, fear of side effects, and family opposition—limit adoption. Education is the strongest factor linked to positive family planning outcomes. The study emphasizes that effective interventions must address cultural and social dynamics by involving men, families, and religious leaders. Long-term improvements depend on enhancing female education alongside targeted family planning efforts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Community-Based Awareness Programs

Initiate culturally sensitive and community-driven awareness campaigns to educate rural women on the benefits and methods of family planning.

2. Training of Lady Health Workers (LHWs)

Strengthen the capacity of LHWs through regular training to disseminate accurate and relatable family planning information.

3. Involvement of Male Partners

Encourage the participation of male partners in family planning education to promote joint decision-making in reproductive health.

4. Improved Accessibility of Contraceptives

Ensure the availability and affordability of a wide range of contraceptive methods in local health facilities.

5. Use of Local Language and Media

Utilize local languages and media platforms such as radio and mobile campaigns to communicate family planning messages effectively.

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